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METHODS OF FORMING LEADERSHIP LIFE OF YOUNG PEOPLE AS A PREREQUISITE FOR CONTINUOUS EDUCATION

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У даній статті автор розглядає можливість мотивації особистості молодшої людини до безперервної освіти через формування та розвиток лідерських якостей. Лідерські позиції молоді сприяють залученню людини до постійного оновлення знань та переробки великого масиву інформації, адже лідерство, так само як і професійні навички потребують постійного саморозвитку для сталості у стійкості своєї позиції та динамічності у практичному застосуванні означеної якості. Ми розглядаємо провідний механізм набуття лідерських якостей як передумову безперервності освіти молодшої людини через призму психолого-педагогічних активних, креативних способів, кожен з яких якісно забезпечує відповідний щабель розвитку лідерства.

Автор акцентує увагу на неперервній освіті як способу збереження, розвитку і взаємозбагачення національних культур та загальнолюдських цінностей, а також як способу збереження трудових ресурсів та розвиток людського капіталу. Сьогодні Україна має багато проблем, частина з яких через безвідповідальність та байдужість громадян. Серед такої категорії громадян є значний відсоток молоді.

Розглядаються такі провідні способи формування та розвитку лідерства як: соціально-психологічний тренінг, створення хабів, застосування воркшопів, метод «Шість капелюх», «World safe», обґрунтовується необхідність створення молодіжних шкіл інноваційного характеру - «Молодіжні школи соціальної активності», метод «Гамбургер», а також: e-learning, m-learning, u-learning, зміна робочих зон, перевернутий клас, автономна група, індивідуальна траєкторія.

Окрім цього, автор акцентує увагу на важливості створення сучасного громадського простору (платформи) для підвищення загального рівня освіченості та соціальної активності молоді відповідного регіону, на який спрямовано інноваційні технології формування та розвитку соціально активної позиції молоді відповідно до європейських стандартів через використання та поповнення людського капіталу.

У статті розглядається значення формування та розвитку талантів лідерства, враховуючи місцеві особливості розвитку регіону, категорії дітей, їх інтереси та наявність ресурсів для самореалізації наших дітей. Комплексність та систематичність взаємодії такого механізму дозволяє отримати практичний результат та забезпечити якісну передумову до самомотиваційного процесу безперервної освіти особистості.

За умов безперервності освітнього процесу збільшується реалізація трудового потенціалу, зростає можливість отримання нових знань, професійного досвіду та покращення кваліфікації, що в свою чергу зменшує міграційні процеси. А забезпечення безперервності освіти автор пропонує здійснювати через формування та розвиток лідерства

Ключові слова: безперервна освіта, безпека країни, лідерські якості, людський капітал, самомотивація, саморозвиток

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1. Introduction

In the acquisition of leadership qualities, which is one of the leading factors in a person's success in various walks of life, there is a direct relationship with continuing education. After all, education throughout life provides confidence in themselves, their strengths, which in turn are factors of leadership qualities of a person. Leadership lifestyles require and provide continuous updating and improvement of knowledge in today's changing world. This is a kind of competitiveness in the arena of leadership positions of an individual, which allows to position strengths in the professional activity, active public, socio-political, cultural life of the country.

A person who exhibits leadership in life is constantly self-motivated for continuing education, because the position of leadership, which is a significant

lever for an active action in different areas of life, requires continuous updating of knowledge, constant entry into a large flow of information. Therefore, forming a personality as a leader is one of the direct prerequisites for self-improvement, including through continuing education.

2. Literary review

The analysis of modern practices indicates the need to invest in people to achieve a harmonious development of the world as a whole [1]. That is why it is very important today to stimulate an individual to continuous improvement.

The continuity of education has often been seen as a kind of plan to cover the education system for the formation of human knowledge. But the current state

indicates that without constant updating and improvement of the system of knowledge, processing of a large mass of information – a person remains out of the system and this has a number of negative consequences [2]. Scientists say that computerization and free access to the Internet greatly facilitates the educational process and awareness of an individual, but subsequently this flow of information has become global, in which people are often lost, do not have time to absorb and process information, passivity to knowledge is formed, especially because of the accessibility of information [3, 4].

Since the beginning of the 2000s, American scientists have placed a considerable emphasis on the importance and ability of forming a leader's position in the personal development, since such a quality allows one to quickly find solutions to problematic situations, keep up with the challenges of society, become interested in the environment and become involved in life around him/her [5, 6].

Thus, analyzing the achievements of Ukrainian and foreign scholars on the importance of continuity of education and the importance of leadership, it is important to consider the motivational aspect of continuing education precisely through the formation and development of leadership. Leadership allows you to creatively, richly, effectively solve a number of problems, namely: increasing the possibility of self-realization, including professional, and the urge to continuous education as an opportunity for a high level of competitiveness in the labor market.

3. The purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to discover ways of forming leadership as a prerequisite for self-motivation for continuing education.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To describe the relationship between the continuity of education and leadership qualities of an individual.
2. To discover leading ways of acquiring leadership qualities among young people.
3. To determine the impact of the proposed methods of formation and development of leadership as a self-motivation for continuing education through the lens of leadership.

4. Materials and methods

Consideration of a motivation for continuing education through leadership is a new approach to developing a defined quality. After all, a person with leadership qualities, striving constantly to remain at the level of leadership, to be competitive among other leaders, is always motivated to self-development, constant updating of knowledge, solid character in achieving the goal. These qualities are an effective prerequisite for lifelong learning.

Continuing education is a set of means, methods and forms of obtaining, deepening and expanding general education, professional competence, culture, education, civic and moral maturity. For each person, continuing education is the process of forming and satisfying his or her cognitive needs and spiritual needs, developing the means and abilities in a network of educational

institutions of different forms of ownership or through self-education [7].

For an individual, the acquisition of leadership qualities is a prerequisite for motivational processes for continuous learning, which is guided by continuous education, whether formal or informal. For the state, such education is a leading field of social policy for ensuring favorable conditions for the general and professional development of each individual, which in turn provides citizens with greater opportunities to realize their knowledge, creative potential, use the full range of human resources for professional recognition and improvement.

For the world society, continuing education is a way of preserving, developing and enriching national cultures and human values, an important factor and condition for international cooperation in the field of education, as well as for solving the global challenges of today [7].

The Memorandum on Continuing Education of the Commission of the European Union identifies the leading areas for the development of continuing education. For example, one of these areas is to increase investment in the human resources development with the aim of raising the priority of Europe's most important asset – people [8]. Thus, the formation and development of personality leadership is an important contribution to the resource as an opportunity to use it twice as much to create the necessary conditions for our country.

One of the important directions of acquiring leadership qualities as a prerequisite for the realization of a continuous learning personality is the development of communication skills, aimed at the professional and business sphere, the quality of which will ensure a high likelihood of a positive communicative impression and ability in a competitive environment.

For this purpose, a number of methods are useful and extremely effective. We describe several of them. The World cafe method is a good start for developing communicative confidence and empowering you in this area. The main position of this method is determined by dividing the group of people into sub-groups at different tables (which in turn allows you to get acquainted with the level and capabilities of each in communication) and discuss different topics. The first attempt at a particular method in the development of communication skills should apply the following topics for each table, which are then exchanged, passing from one table to another, these are: rules of telephone communication, leading words and expressions in business communication and the possibilities of their use in everyday life, words - goodwill and respect and practical application. Each table is a specific problematic issue, as the team moves from place to place, not only familiar with a number of new requirements and rules for business communication, but also has the practical ability to immediately apply knowledge. The supervising and coordinating function is performed by the mentor.

The Hamburger method is interesting and accessible to young people in the formation and development of communications about the feedback effect, which is crucial for a positive outcome in the communication process. There are three levels to the communication process: the positive side, the

development side and the motivation side. Participants of a dialogue are given different topics of communication their task is to learn to concentrate their language on these three aspects. Yes, in the positive side, considerable attention should be paid to the good aspects of the activity (desire, responsibility. For example, "Great colleague, you use innovative approaches in your work"). Later in the conversation, participants should learn to focus on aspects that require reinforcement, improvement, that is, growth points (for example: it seems to me that... because ..) and as a final point of influence in communication, by learning and practicing the method, it is recommended, that you propose your "improvement" option.

It is worth mentioning about the Six Hats method and its capabilities in developing communication skills. Applying this method allows you to get rid of these three communication problems, such as unnecessary emotions, confusion and inconsistency. Each color has its own characteristic [9]. In the process of discussion, white hat is given first, then black and yellow, and the last one is to listen to the blue hat. Depending on which composition the specified method will be directed, ie team or individual - the leading expected results are determined.

The problem of young people's indifference causes a number of problems in Ukraine. Analyzing the cause of this phenomenon, it becomes clear that one of the reasons is ignorance. It is possible to overcome ignorance by introducing everyone into continuing education. After all, continuous education is a way of self-development, self-realization and self-motivation, assimilation of a large amount of knowledge and skills. Creating innovative youth schools - "Youth Schools for Social Activity" can be effective. Such a form will ensure the participation of the younger generation to uninterrupted self-growth, as activity requires knowledge that is constantly updated and brings changes to society. Such schools should meet with active public figures, who already have some experience in implementing social projects. In such schools it is important to create a living library, where there will be face-to-face communication with representatives of Ukraine and Europe on the implementation of social projects to form a socially active position of young people and focus on lifelong learning; to create social initiatives in schools, which will be driven by the most active participants and thus stimulate the comprehensive development of other participants in such schools.

In addition to innovative schools, in our opinion, it is necessary to create a modern public space for raising the general level of education and social activity of the population of the region, which is directed by innovative technologies of formation and development of socially active position of youth in accordance with European standards through the use and replenishment of the human capital.

Also, to solve educational tasks within educational institutions for the development of the human capital as a factor of formation of the socially active youth, it is necessary to use such interactive forms of educational activity that more widely and creatively reveal the human capital in the future, namely: case technologies; "Round Table"; debate; business games; case study; trainings; video conferences; "brain storm";

focus groups; role games; group discussions; method of projects.

In addition to the main ones mentioned above, the following innovative ones should be added: e-learning; m-learning; u-learning; f-learning; blended-learning; Change of work zones (The Station Rotation Model); The Flipped Classroom Model; The Lab Rotation Model; The Individual-Rotation Model [10].

It is important to increase the focus on the development of continuing education in rural areas, since the lack of work and decent wages, the destruction of infrastructure causes the outflow of staff, and therefore the impossibility of full motivational impact on self-development. One of the leading mechanisms for overcoming such a problem is the creation of cultural and educational hubs, which contain a unique center of development. In such centers, in addition to the above methods, the use of hackathons is relevant. It is because of this method that participants have a time limit to solve the problem and constant support from the mentors.

For the formation and development of leadership talents, taking into account the local peculiarities of the development of the region, the categories of children, their interests and the lack or availability of resources for self-realization of our children, we propose for the implementation of the hub a set of the following measures: formation of a group of workshops; formation and development of communicative plinging; a complex of training work on the leading theme "I am a leader"; holding a Leaders Forum; organization of creation of the Youth Council, Youth Parliament; the use of workshops; conducting sports, creative and scientific tournaments

The necessary mechanism for determining the present advantages and disadvantages of using one's time and directions of life is the Wheel of Life methodology. In this exercise, participants determine which area of their lives they have more time to realize, and which less, they are aware of their life goals.

5. Results of the study and their discussion

Analyzing a number of ways that leadership has been developed and used, and the emphasis on interaction between leaders - lifelong youth education, the following benefits can be observed.

As a result of these activities, young people gain knowledge through the high intensity of group interaction, activity and independence of participants, gain the actual experience and personal experience, ensure awareness of the realization of their dreams and plans with their human resources and leading qualities. The psychological awareness of young people of their importance in their own life and in the life of Ukraine as a whole is fixed, the motivation to acquire leadership qualities and use them in all spheres of life is determined.

Lifelong education, that is, continuing education is the ability to find oneself not only for a short period of time, which is static in the modern development of information technologies, but also to be at the "center" always, despite changes. A person, who is confident in his/her abilities, guided by innovative skills to enter the community and be practically realized, will not be afraid of modern challenges and difficulties on the way to overcoming certain obstacles due to the rapid scientific

and technological process. Such a person will always feel needed and valuable, because he / she understands that can have a qualitative impact on a particular process in one's personal, professional, socio-cultural, political or public life.

Accordingly, a sense of importance to the own country, including through knowledge, the ability to use practically constantly updated knowledge, which in turn will provide jobs and recognition in a particular socio-occupational circle, - is a step towards reducing labor migration.

Thus, the development of young person's leadership skills is a prerequisite for a motivational process for lifelong learning, which in turn contributes to reducing labor migration. One of the reasons for this is the loss of professional skills and qualifications in a constantly changing dynamic world. Given the continuity of the educational process, the work potential realization is increasing, the possibility of acquiring new knowledge, professional experience and qualification is increasing, the constant increase and updating of knowledge is a step towards active citizenship, thereby enabling people to participate directly in the political life of the country.

Thus, the continuity of education is a step towards reducing labor migration through continuous updating of knowledge, which will increase the level of professional and civic activity. In turn, we offer the continuity of education through the leadership formation and development.

6. Conclusions

1. One of the leading conditions for providing a motivation for the continuous development of the individual as the basis for a safe direction of the country's

development is the formation and acquisition of leadership qualities of an individual, especially a young human as the engine of the driving force of development. The leader is able to provide self-motivation for the leading actions of life, including continuous learning, which is the key to success in the modern information world.

2. The mentioned mechanisms of realization of the given task are considered as ways of acquiring a leading position in their social, professional, cultural life and are formed as various exercises, practical intellectual pursuits, active physical and social and psychological measures. All of the above are not exhaustive in the development of a motivation for continuing education, but are substantially sufficient to lay a solid foundation for the formation and enhancement of the leader's quality as a motivational aspect for self-development throughout life.

3. The proposed ways of implementing the mechanism of an influence of leadership on the development of lifelong education, including such as: creation of public space, schools of active youth, socio-psychological active forms of intellectual, physical and creative activity motivate to self-development and continuity of education, since participation in each event, the solution of each problem constantly emphasizes the importance of new knowledge, skills that can be useful and important in practical problem solving.

Thus, a person with a constant desire and practical realization of continuous education is a competitive person, who will always find his/her place in society and will be able to realize his/her abilities, knowledge, ability to improve the life of this society.

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